

Title:

Advancing Fenceline Community Resilience to Heat, Humidity, and Air Pollution Co-exposure in Saint James Parish (ARC-Saint James)

In 2023, the Gulf South experienced an unprecedented number of days where heat coupled with high humidity made it unsafe to work or play outdoors for several days at a time. Air pollution, exacerbated by these climatic conditions, poses an increasing threat under climate change, particularly to the many underserved fenceline Environmental Justice (EJ) communities found across the Gulf South. Recent research from the proposal team suggests that heat, especially when combined with high humidity, has super additive effects from co-exposure to air pollution. Of particular concern, Ozone (O₃) pollution is produced via the photochemical cycle of nitrogen oxides which is accelerated in the presence of heat and volatile organic chemicals such as those produced by petrochemical industrial activities. Advancing Fenceline Community Resilience to Heat, Humidity, and Air Pollution Co-exposure in Saint James Parish (ARC-Saint James) builds upon the longstanding partnership of Louisiana Bucket Brigade and Tulane University to support underserved EJ communities to leverage NASA Earth science for monitoring and developing evidence-based strategic solutions to confront negative impacts of cumulative effects as a critical climate change resilience capacity. Co-developing a fundamental advance in integrated Earth/Environmental/Social/Health science for understanding patterns of exposure to cumulative effects will strengthen capacities for scientifically valid preparedness, mitigation, and response action by EJ fenceline communities, associated boundary organizations, and broader stakeholder groups. This builds on proven fenceline community engagement in air quality monitoring using simple 'bucket' sampling technology and crowdsourced I-witness pollution mapping platform deployed by the members of this project team during the Deep Water Horizon oil spill disaster.

Our project Co-I hails from the Louisiana River Parishes and leads engagement in participating fenceline communities of Saint James Parish. Four of the seven census tracts in the parish are designated as disadvantaged in this heavy-industry corridor along the Mississippi River referred to as Cancer Alley. Our project builds on an initiative to directly involve college students from the area in paid positions as Youth Open Science Leaders (YOSLs) that will build capacity for sustainability of community climate resilience solutions. Leveraging NASA data and approaches, we aim to co-create sustainable, cost-effective monitoring and decision support, reducing reliance on in situ measurements over time.

The technical approach leverages the high temporal resolution of MODIS/VIIIRS, with the medium spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 Landsat ECOSTress data for environmental variables and estimates of PM_{2.5} to be used in risk index development. Air pollution analysis will begin with the Aura Ozone Monitoring Instrument in anticipation of NO₂, SO₂ measurements by the TEMPO mission. An in situ network of ground sensors maintained by YOSLs and community monitors will validate and contribute to index-driven mapping products for the community climate resilience solution applications, including index integration with socio-economic health outcome data at the census tract level, creating a comprehensive evidence base for resilience decision support.

The three project objectives/components deliverables are a Climate Risk and Resilience Assessment, Community Climate Resilience Solution, and closely related program of critical reflective evaluation and capacity development.

Clear tasking and milestones ensure excellent project management by an experienced team with nearly 15 years together and more than 50 years combined experience in leveraging multi-source data streams for community-engaged and open science for health, environmental justice, and community resilience.